

THE USE OF ASPECT IN “WOMEN IN LOVE” BY DAVID LAWRENCE

Jabborova Aziza Jobirovna

The lecturer of History and Philology department, Asia International University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8026299>

Abstract. This article is a logical continuation of my former article named “The category of aspect in English grammar” “In this article, the novel “Women in love” by David Lawrence is analyzed according to the category of aspect. The statements from this novel are categorized and examined by mentioning the function of each part of speech used in the sentence.

Key words: supplement, main verb, perfective aspect, synthetic way, past perfect aspect, past simple, auxiliary verb, future perfect aspect, present perfect aspect, positive sentence, future progressive aspect, subject, sentence, past progressive aspect, present progressive aspect, negative-interrogative sentence, present perfect progressive, past perfect progressive aspect, past simple aspect, present simple aspect, interrogative meaning, predicate.

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ АСПЕКТА В ФИЛЬМЕ ДЭВИДА ЛОУРЕНСА “ВЛЮБЛЕННЫЕ ЖЕНЩИНЫ”

Аннотация. Эта статья является логическим продолжением моей предыдущей статьи под названием “Категория аспекта в грамматике английского языка” “В этой статье роман Дэвида Лоуренса “Влюбленные женщины” анализируется в соответствии с категорией аспекта. Высказывания, составляющие этот роман, классифицируются и анализируются путем упоминания функции каждой части речи, используемой в предложении.

Ключевые слова: дополнение, основной глагол, совершенный вид, синтетический способ, прошедшее совершенное время, прошедшее простое, вспомогательный глагол, будущее совершенное время, настоящее совершенное время, положительное предложение, будущее прогрессивное время, подлежащее, предложение, прошедшее прогрессивное время, настоящее прогрессивное время, отрицательно-вопросительное предложение, настоящее совершенное прогрессивное время, прошедший совершенный прогрессивный аспект, прошедший простой аспект, настоящий простой аспект, вопросительное значение, сказуемое.

Introduction

Aspect in the English language has been described through different categories and terminologies, which might lead teachers and students into some misunderstandings. Considering the importance of understanding the systematic representation of this concept in learning a foreign language, I review and compare the various ways aspect is presented in some descriptive English grammar books. The main source of the article consists of different books as Svetlana L`vovna K. "The Morphology of modern English language", Irisqulov "Theoretical Grammar" and M. Naumenka "Theoretical Grammar of English". As an example of analysis, I have chosen one of the most famous English writers David Lawrence. I aimed at analyzing the use of aspect in the literary work “Women in Love” by David Lawrence. This way I intend to survey the use of aspect in a literary work by a definite author and reveal his writing style. Besides that to state the practical use of the theme I have addressed to internet sources and modern books on teaching English.

Hopefully, this article can be a hint or a light for further scientific innovations from theoretical and methodological view points.

The use of perfective aspect in the story

-----So you have come home, expecting him here?’(1)

Present Perfect aspect. Formation: The verb `Have` is used in The Present Tense.

`Have come`-perfect. The verb-`Have` is supplement. The main verb `Come` is used in a synthetic way, it is in the past participle form. The number of the verb is identified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `Have` is an auxiliary verb here.

The use: perfective form is used in the situation that has happened by this time, and it is applied in the interrogative sentence (by intonation of the speaker).

------(Moving with her artist friends in different kinds of society,) Gudrun had already come to know a good many people of repute and standing. (2)

Past Perfect aspect. Formation: The verb `Have` is used in The Past Tense.

`Had come`-perfective. The verb-`Had` is supplement. The main verb `come` is used in a synthetic way, it is used in the past participle form here. The number of the verb is identified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `Had` is an auxiliary verb here.

The use: perfective form is used in the situation that had happened and finished earlier than the event happened in the past and it is applied in the positive sentence.

-----She had suffered so bitterly (when he did not come, that still she was dazed).(3)

Past Perfect aspect. Formation: The verb `Have` is used in The Past Tense.

`Had suffered`-perfective. The verb-`Had` is supplement. The main verb `suffer` is used in a synthetic way, it is used in the past participle form here, adding `-ed` inflection. The number of the verb is identified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `Had` is an auxiliary verb here.

The use: perfective form is used in the situation that had happened and finished earlier than the event happened in the past and it is applied in the positive sentence.

-----He has never had a friend. (4)

Present Perfect aspect. Formation: The verb `Have` is used in The Present Tense.

`Has had`-perfect. The verb-`has` is supplement. The main verb `Have` is used in a synthetic way, it is in the past participle form. The number of the verb is identified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `Has` is an auxiliary verb here.

The use: perfective form is used in the situation that has happened by this time, and it is applied in the negative sentence (by the help of the word `Never`).

-----Laura won't have brought such a fool into the family as Lottie did. (7)

Future Perfect aspect. Formation: The verb `Have` is used in The Future Tense.

`Will not have brought`-perfect. The verb-`will have` is supplement and takes `Not` adverb. The main verb `Have` is used in a synthetic way, it is in the past participle form. The number of the verb is identified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `will have` is an auxiliary verb here.

The use: perfective form is used in the situation that will have happened and finished by particular time in the future, and it is applied in the negative- interrogative sentence by putting the future form of `Have` before the subject and adding `Not` adverb.

-----This day had gone by like so many more, in an activity that was like a trance. (8)

Past Perfect aspect. Formation: The verb `Have` is used in The Past Tense.

`Had gone`-perfective. The verb-`Had` is supplement. The main verb `Go` is used in a synthetic way, it is used in the past participle form here. The number of the verb is indentified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `Had` is an auxiliary verb here.

The use: perfective form is used in the situation that had happened and finished earlier than the event happened in the past and it is used in the positive sentence.

-----Had you never noticed them before? (9)

Past Perfect aspect. Formation: The verb `Have` is used in The Past Tense.

`Had noticed`-perfective. The verb-`Had` is supplement. The main verb `Notice` is used in a synthetic way, it is used in the past participle form here, adding `-ed` inflection. The number of the verb is indentified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `Had` is an auxiliary verb and gives question meaning here.

The use: perfective form is used in the situation that had happened and finished earlier than the event happened in the past and it is used in the negative sentence by putting `had` before the subject.

-----Your sister has come home? (10)

Present Perfect aspect. Formation: The verb `Have` is used in The Present Tense.

`Has come`-perfect. The verb-`has` is supplement. The main verb `Come` is used in a synthetic way, it is in the past participle form. The number of the verb is indentified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `Has` is an auxiliary verb here.

The use: perfective form is used in the situation that has happened by this time, and it is applied in the Interrogative sentence (by the intonation of speaker).

-----You've worked all day. (11)

Present Perfect aspect. Formation: The verb `Have` is used in The Present Tense.

`Have worked`-perfect. The verb-`have` is supplement. The main verb `Work` is used in a synthetic way, it is in the past participle form, adding `-ed` inflection. The number of the verb is indentified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `Have` is an auxiliary verb here.

The use: perfective form is used in the situation that has happened by this time, and it is applied in the positive sentence.

-----She would have liked them all annihilated, cleared away, so that the world was left clear for her.(12)

Future Perfect aspect. Formation: The verb `Have` is used in The Future in the past Tense.

`Would have liked`-perfective. The verb-` would have` is supplement. The main verb `Like` is used in a synthetic way, it is in the past participle form by adding `-d` inflection. The number of the verb is indentified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `Would have` is an auxiliary verb here.

The use: perfective form is used in the future unreal situation in the past, namely the speaker dreams to change the situation which happened in the past and thinks about possible ending. It is applied in the positive sentence.

----- (And he wouldn't go away,) he would have stayed for ever. (13)

Future Perfect aspect. Formation: The verb `Have` is used in The Future in the past Tense.

`Would have stayed`-perfective. The verb-` would have` is supplement. The main verb `stay` is used in a synthetic way, it is in the past participle form by adding `-ed` inflection. The number of the verb is identified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `Would have` is an auxiliary verb here.

The use: perfective form is used in the future unreal situation in the past, namely the speaker dreams to change the situation which happened in the past and thinks about possible ending. It is applied in the positive sentence.

----- But she would have been glad of ten pounds, and he would have been VERY glad to give them to her. (14)

Future Perfect aspect. Formation: The verb `Have` is used in The Future in the past Tense.

`Would have been glad`-perfective. The verb-` would have` is supplement. The main verb `Been glad` is used in a synthetic way, it is in the past participle form. The number of the verb is identified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `Would have` is an auxiliary verb here.

The use: perfective form is used in the future unreal situation in the past, namely the speaker dreams to change the situation which happened in the past and thinks about possible ending. It is applied in the positive sentence.

The use of progressive aspect in the story

----- I was hoping now for a man to come along (15)

Past Progressive aspect. Formation: The verb `To be` is used in The Past Tense.

`Was hoping`-continuous. To be-`was` is supplement. The main verb `Hope` is used in a synthetic way, it takes `-ing` inflection. The number of the verb is identified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `To be-was` is an auxiliary verb here.

The use: continuous form is used in an unreal progressive condition, namely speaker dreams that situation is happening at this moment, but, actually, it is not, and it is applied in the positive sentence.

----- The two girls were soon walking swiftly down the main road of Beldover, a wide street, part shops, part dwelling-houses, utterly formless and sordid, without poverty. (16)

Past Progressive aspect. Formation: The verb `To be` is used in the Past tense.

`Were walking`-continuous. `To be-were` is supplement. The main verb `walk` is used in a synthetic way, it takes `-ing` inflection. The number of the verb is identified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `To be-were` is an auxiliary verb here.

The use: continuous form is used in future meaning, namely speaker plans the situation will happen in a particular time in the future, and it is applied in the positive sentence.

-----We shall be sitting down to eat in a minute, (17)

Future progressive aspect. Formation: The verb `To be` is used in the Future tense.

`Shall be sitting`-continuous. `To be-shall be` is supplement. The main verb `sit` is used in a synthetic way, it takes `-ing` inflection. The number of the verb is identified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `To be-shall be` - is an auxiliary verb here.

The use: continuous form is used in future plan, to show the event will be occurring to the certain time in the future and in a positive sentence.

-----You are doing catkins?'(18)

Present Progressive aspect. Formation: The verb `To be` is used in the Present tense.

`Are doing`-continuous. `To be-are` is supplement. The main verb `do` is used in a synthetic way, it takes `-ing` inflection. The number of the verb is identified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `To be-are` - is an auxiliary verb here.

The use: continuous form is used in the situation that is happening now, in an interrogative sentence (by intonation of the speaker).

-----I was only resting a minute. (19)

Past Progressive aspect. Formation: The verb `To be` is used in the Past tense.

`Was resting`-continuous. `To be-was` is supplement. The main verb `rest` is used in a synthetic way, it takes `-ing` inflection. The number of the verb is identified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `To be-was` - is an auxiliary verb here.

The use: continuous form is used to highlight the situation was happening in the past at the certain period of time, and it is applied in the positive sentence.

-----We are going to drink toasts. (20)

Present Progressive aspect. Formation: The verb `To be` is used in the Present tense.

`Are going`-continuous. `To be-are` is supplement. The main verb `Go` is used in a synthetic way, it takes `-ing` inflection, and it takes `to` - preposition. The number of the verb is identified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `To be-are` - is an auxiliary verb here. `To` - preposition in the verb `Go` gives particular meaning.

The use: continuous form is used in future meaning, namely speaker plans the situation will happen in a particular time in the future, and it is applied in the positive sentence.

-----('No. I want them out of the way, and) you're always shoving them in it.'(21)

Present Progressive aspect. Formation: The verb `To be` is used in The Present Tense.

`Are shoving`-continuous. To be-`are` is supplement. The main verb `Shove` is used in a synthetic way, it takes `-ing` inflection. The number of the verb is identified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `To be-are` is an auxiliary verb and in a question meaning here.

The use: continuous form is used to show speaker's frustration or complaint about somebody's habit in order to ask them to stop it. It is applied in the positive sentence.

-----Aren't we exchanging the substance for the shadow, aren't we forfeiting life for this dead quality of knowledge? (22)

Present Progressive aspect. Formation: The verb `To be` is used in The Present Tense.

`Aren't exchanging`-continuous. To be-`are` is supplement and takes `Not` adverb. The main verb `Exchange` is used in a synthetic way, it takes `-ing` inflection. The number of the verb is identified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `To be-are` is an auxiliary verb and in a question meaning here. `Not` adds negative meaning to the sentence.

The use: continuous form is used in the situation that is happening around the time of speaking, but not necessarily exactly at the time of speaking, namely the situation is occurring these days, and it is applied in the Negative- Interrogative sentence.

-----I shall be leaving tomorrow. (23)

Future progressive aspect. Formation: The verb `To be` is used in the Future tense.

`Shall be leaving`-continuous. `To be-shall be` is supplement. The main verb `leave` is used in a synthetic way, it takes `-ing` inflection. The number of the verb is identified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `To be-shall be`- is an auxiliary verb here.

The use: continuous form is used in future plan, to show the event will be occurring to the certain time in the future and in a positive sentence.

----- (I wondered if) anybody would be looking for you. (24)

Future progressive aspect. Formation: The verb `To be` is used in the Future in the Past tense.

`Would be looking`-continuous. `To be-would be` is supplement. The main verb `look for` is used in a synthetic way, it takes `-ing` inflection and `for`-preposition. The number of the verb is identified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `To be-would be`- is an auxiliary verb, and `Look for` is phrasal verb here.

The use: continuous form is used in future progressive in the past, namely speaker says his past thoughts that the event would be happening in the future, and in a positive sentence.

-----Father is lying down, (he is not quite well.) (25)

Present Progressive aspect. Formation: The verb `To be` is used in The Present Tense.

`Is lying`-continuous. To be-`is` is supplement. The main verb `Lie` is used in a synthetic way, it takes `-ing` inflection. The number of the verb is identified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `To be-are` is an auxiliary verb here.

The use: continuous form is used in the situation that is happening exactly around at the time of speaking, namely the situation is occurring at this moment, and it is applied in the positive sentence.

-----She was still wearing her hat, and her sac coat of blue silk. (26)

Past Progressive aspect. Formation: The verb `To be` is used in the Past tense.

`Was wearing`-continuous. `To be-was` is supplement. The main verb `Wear` is used in a synthetic way, it takes `-ing` inflection. The number of the verb is identified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `To be-was` - is an auxiliary verb here.

The use: continuous form is used to highlight the situation was happening in the past at the certain period of time, and it is applied in the positive sentence.

-----As best man, he would be standing beside the altar. (27)

Future progressive aspect. Formation: The verb `To be` is used in the Future in the Past tense.

`Would be standing`-continuous. `To be-would be` is supplement. The main verb `stand` is used in a synthetic way, it takes `-ing` inflection. The number of the verb is identified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `To be-would be` - is an auxiliary verb here.

The use: continuous form is used in future progressive in the past, namely speaker says his past thoughts that the event would be happening in the future, and in a positive sentence.

-----Hermione was having a discussion with the bridegroom about nationality. (28)

Past Progressive aspect. Formation: The verb `To be` is used in the Past tense.

`Was having`-continuous. `To be-was` is supplement. The main verb `Have` is used in a synthetic way, it takes `-ing` inflection. The number of the verb is identified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `To be-was` - is an auxiliary verb here.

The use: continuous form is used to highlight the situation was happening in the past at the certain period of time, and it is applied in the positive sentence.

-----*(The atmosphere was grey and translucent, the birds sang sharply on the young twigs,)* the earth would be quickening and hastening in growth. (29)

Future progressive aspect Formation: The verb `To be` is used in the Future in the Past tense.

`Would be quickening/hastening`-continuous. `To be-would be` is supplement. The main verbs `Quicken and Hasten` are used in a synthetic way, they take `-ing` inflection. The number of the verb is identified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `To be-would be` - is an auxiliary verb here.

The use: continuous form is used in future progressive in the past, namely speaker says his past thoughts that the event would be happening in the future, and it is applied in a positive sentence.

The use of perfect progressive aspect in the story

-----*(The desks were littered with catkins, hazel and willow, which)* the children had been sketching. (36)

Past Perfect Progressive aspect. Formation: The verb `Have` is used in The Past Perfect Continuous Tense.

`Had been sketching`-perfect progressive. The verb-` had been` is supplement. The main verb `Sketch` is used in a synthetic way, it takes `-ing` inflection. The number of the verb is identified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `Had been` is an auxiliary verb here.

The use: perfect progressive form is used to show how long something had been happening before something else happened. It is applied in the positive sentence.

-----I have been thinking, Gerald,' she said, with an insulting nonchalance, 'that I shall not go back to England.' (37)

Present Perfect Progressive aspect. Formation: The verb `Have` is used in The Present Perfect Continuous Tense.

`Have been thinking`-perfect progressive. The verb-` have been` is supplement. The main verb `Think` is used in a synthetic way, it takes `-ing` inflection. The number of the verb is identified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `Have been` is an auxiliary verb here.

The use: perfect progressive form is used to show how long something has been happening before something else happens. It is applied in the positive sentence.

-----*(You see it was an old thing that) It had been lying in the stable for years.* (38)

Past Perfect Progressive aspect. Formation: The verb `Have` is used in The Past Perfect Continuous Tense.

`Had been lying`-perfect progressive. The verb-` had been` is supplement. The main verb `Lie` is used in a synthetic way, it takes `-ing` inflection and the root sees some changes `Lie>lying`. The number of the verb is identified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `Had been` is an auxiliary verb here.

The use: perfect progressive form is used to show how long something had been happening before something else happened. It is applied in the positive sentence.

-----*He might have been saying anything whatsoever.* (39)

Present Perfect Progressive aspect. Formation: The verb `Have` is used in The Present Perfect Continuous Tense.

`Might have been saying`-perfect progressive. Modal verb `Might` and the verb `have been` are supplement. The main verb `Say` is used in a synthetic way, it takes `-ing` inflection. The number of the verb is identified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `Have been` is an auxiliary verb here, modal verb `Might` adds the meaning of the possibility to happen something.

The use: perfect progressive form is used to show the possibility of how long something has been happening before something else happens. It is applied in the positive sentence.

-----*She had been wearing a loose dressing-gown of purple silk, tied round her waist.* (40)

Past Perfect Progressive aspect. Formation: The verb `Have` is used in The Past Perfect Continuous Tense.

`Had been wearing`-perfect progressive. The verb-` had been` is supplement. The main verb `Wear` is used in a synthetic way, it takes `-ing` inflection. The number of the verb is identified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `Had been` is an auxiliary verb here.

The use: perfect progressive form is used to show how long something had been happening before something else happened. It is applied in the positive sentence.

-----*(He took up a large volume which) he had been reading before, and became minutely attentive to his author.* (41)

Past Perfect Progressive aspect. Formation: The verb `Have` is used in The Past Perfect Continuous Tense.

‘Had been reading’-perfect progressive. The verb-‘ had been’ is supplement. The main verb ‘Read’ is used in a synthetic way, it takes ‘-ing’ inflection. The number of the verb is identified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb ‘Had been’ is an auxiliary verb here.

The use: perfect progressive form is used to show how long something had been happening before something else happened. It is applied in the positive sentence.

-----Gerald might still have been living in the spirit with Birkin, even after death. (42)

Present Perfect Progressive aspect. Formation: The verb ‘Have’ is used in The Present Perfect Continuous Tense.

‘Might have been living’-perfect progressive. Modal verb ‘Might’ and the verb ‘have been’ are supplement. The main verb ‘live’ is used in a synthetic way, it takes ‘-ing’ inflection. The number of the verb is identified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb ‘Have been’ is an auxiliary verb here, modal verb ‘Might’ adds the meaning of the possibility to happen something.

The use: perfect progressive form is used to show the possibility of how long something has been happening before something else happens. It is applied in the positive sentence.

-----Birkin had been teasing Ursula. (43)

Past Perfect Progressive aspect. Formation: The verb ‘Have’ is used in The Past Perfect Continuous Tense.

‘Had been teasing’-perfect progressive. The verb-‘ had been’ is supplement. The main verb ‘Tease’ is used in a synthetic way, it takes ‘-ing’ inflection. The number of the verb is identified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb ‘Had been’ is an auxiliary verb here.

The use: perfect progressive form is used to show how long something had been happening before something else happened. It is applied in the positive sentence.

-----‘(Do you mean,’ said Gerald, with the punctiliousness of a man) who has been drinking,(‘that you are afraid of the sight of a black-beetle, or you are afraid of a black-beetle biting you, or doing you some harm?’)(45)

Present Perfect Progressive aspect. Formation: The verb ‘Have’ is used in The Present Perfect Continuous Tense.

‘Has been drinking’-perfect progressive. The verb ‘has been’ is supplement. The main verb ‘Drink’ is used in a synthetic way, it takes ‘-ing’ inflection. The number of the verb is identified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb ‘Has been’ is an auxiliary verb here.

The use: perfect progressive form is used to show how long something has been happening before something else happens, here to add the information to the former sentence. It is applied in the positive sentence.

-----‘(She realised how all her life) she had been drawing nearer and nearer to this brink, (where there was no beyond, from which one had to leap like Sappho into the unknown.) (46)

Past Perfect Progressive aspect. Formation: The verb ‘Have’ is used in The Past Perfect Continuous Tense.

`Had been drawing`-perfect progressive. The verb-` had been` is supplement. The main verb `Draw` is used in a synthetic way, it takes `-ing` inflection. The number of the verb is indentified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `Had been` is an auxiliary verb here.

The use: perfect progressive form is used to show how long something had been happening before something else happened. It is applied in the positive sentence.

-----Of course he had been loving Gerald all along, and all along denying it.(47)

Past Perfect Progressive aspect. Formation: The verb `Have` is used in The Past Perfect Continuous Tense.

`Had been loving`-perfect progressive. The verb-` had been` is supplement. The main verb `Love` is used in a synthetic way, it takes `-ing` inflection. The number of the verb is indentified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `Had been` is an auxiliary verb here.

The use: perfect progressive form is used to show how long something had been happening before something else happened. It is applied in the positive sentence.

-----He knew that all his life he had been wrenching at the frame of life to break it apart.
(48)

Past Perfect Progressive aspect. Formation: The verb `Have` is used in The Past Perfect Continuous Tense.

`Had been wrenching`-perfect progressive. The verb-` had been` is supplement. The main verb `Wrench` is used in a synthetic way, it takes `-ing` inflection. The number of the verb is indentified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `Had been` is an auxiliary verb here.

The use: perfect progressive form is used to show how long something had been happening before something else happened. It is applied in the positive sentence.

The use of simple aspect in the story

-----I liked him awfully (30)

Past Simple aspect. Formation: The verb `like` is used in The Past Tense.

`Liked`-imperfect, non-progressive. The main verb `like` is used in a synthetic way, it takes `-ed` inflection. The number of the verb is indentified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `Like` is predicate here.

The use: imperfective, non-progressive form is used in the situation that happened in the past, and it is applied in the positive sentence.

-----The man makes it impossible (31)

Present Simple aspect. Formation: The verb `make` is used in The Present Tense.

`Makes`-imperfect, non-progressive. The main verb `make` is used in a synthetic way, it takes `-s` inflection. The number of the verb is indentified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `makes` is predicate here.

The use: imperfective, non-progressive form is used to say something happens all the time or repeatedly, and it is applied in the positive sentence

-----You won't stay long, (32)

Future Simple aspect. Formation: The verb `Stay` is used in The Future Tense.

`Won't stay`-imperfect, non-progressive. `Will` is supplement. `Not` is adverb. `Stay` is the main verb. The number of the verb is indentified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: `Will` is auxiliary verb, takes `not` adding negative meaning.

The use: imperfective, non-progressive form is used in showing something is decided to do at the time of speaking, and it is applied in the negative sentence.

-----I don't know half the people here. (33)

Present Simple aspect. Formation: The verb `know` is used in The Present Tense.

`Don't know`-imperfect, non-progressive. The verb `Do` is supplement and takes `Not` adverb. `Know` is the main verb here. The number of the verb is indentified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `Do` is an auxiliary here, `not` gives negative meaning.

The use: imperfective, non-progressive form is used to say something is true in general, and it is applied in the negative sentence

-----It would be much better (if they were just wiped out).(34)

Future Simple aspect. Formation: The verb `to be` is used in The Future in the Past Tense.

`Would be`-imperfect, non-progressive. The verb `To be- would be` is the main verb. The number of the verb is indentified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: The verb `would be` is predicate here.

The use: imperfective, non-progressive form is used in an unreal situation, namely the speaker dreams to happen something, and it is applied in the positive sentence.

-----Won't you come and take your hat off, mother dear? (35)

Future Simple aspect. Formation: The verb `Come` is used in The Future Tense.

`Won't come`-imperfect, non-progressive. `Will` is supplement, `Not` is adverb. `Come` is the main verb. The number of the verb is indentified by the number of the subject in the sentence.

The function: `Will` is auxiliary verb, adds interrogative meaning.

The use: imperfective, non-progressive form is used in showing something is decided to do at the time of speaking, and it is applied in the negative-interrogative sentence.

CONCLUSION

While analyzing, I have noticed that the concept of aspect has been didactically described and formulated in various ways, which makes the topic become even more complex. For this article, I reviewed and compared the various books presented aspect and its types and found out a few misunderstandings and controversial ideas made by grammarians. In the analysis, it comes into view that, although aspect is approached in a considerably comprehensive way in various grammar books, there is consistent variance in the categorization and terminology adopted by the authors which might cause confusion for students or teachers who use them.

Regarding the terminology adopted in the description of these points of view, some of the secondary variance relies on the use of the term 'perfective' as a synonym for 'perfect.' I think that this confusion might be related to the debate on whether the English language would have the perfective aspect, since there is no special verb form to indicate it. Since perfective is considered a basic aspect by Comrie due to its notability in language systems, this disambiguation may be of considerable importance for students and teachers of English as a foreign language.

REFERENCES

1. Bas A., Sylvia Ch., and Edmund W. (2014). Oxford Dictionary of English Grammar. Oxford University Press 2nd ed.
2. Douglas B., Susan C., and Geoffrey L. (2002). Longman Student Grammar of Spoken and Written English. Longman. Pearson Education Ltd.
3. Douglas B., Stig J., Edward F. and Geoffrey L. (1999). Longman Grammar of Spoken and Written English. Pearson Education Ltd.
4. Randolph Q., Sidney G., Geoffrey L. and Jan S. (1980). A Grammar of Contemporary English . Addison-Wesley Longman Ltd.
5. Sidney G. (1996). The Oxford English Grammar. Oxford University Press.
6. Svetlana L. K. (2010). The Morphology of Modern English Language (МОРФОЛОГИЯ СОВРЕМЕННОГО АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА). Ярославский государственный педагогический университет им. К.Д. Ушинского.
7. Bernard C. (1976). Aspect: an introduction to the study of verbal aspect and related problems. New York: Cambridge University Press.
8. www.studfile.net
9. www.books.google.co.uz
10. www.lawlessenglish.com